

Supplemental Figures

for

Molecular Correlates of Hemorrhage and Edema Volumes following Human Intracerebral Hemorrhage Implicate Inflammation, Autophagy, mRNA Splicing, and T Cell Receptor Signaling

Translational Stroke Research

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Fig. S1 NLRP3 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S2 NLRC4 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S3 NCF2 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S4 CSF3R VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S5 Magenta T Cell Signaling Pathway using ICH correlations

Fig. S6 TRAJ36 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S7 ITK VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S8 LCK VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S9 S1PR1 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S10 SKAP1 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S11 ICH-aPHE Plot and Correlation

Fig. S12A ICH-rPHE Plot and Correlation

Fig. S12B aPHE-rPHE Plot and Correlation

Fig. S14 ICH Hub Enrichment in Immune and Leukocytic Processes

Fig. S16 VCAN VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S17 HMOX1 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S18 RASGRP1 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S20 KCNA3 VisANT Subnetwork

Fig. S21 FBXO21 VisANT Subnetwork

